

Statistics visualization for the CERN Document Server

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The CERN Document Server (CDS) is going through a transition phase, in which the entire underlying software stack is being updated. One of the features highly requested by our users is statistics, either in the form of individual charts per records, or in the form of dashboards for collections.

Taking advantage of the new framework used for building the new CDS (Invenio v3.0) and of the Elasticsearch cluster that is currently gathering CDS user statistics, the student will work on ways of visualising this data. The implementation will be deployed on the new version of CDS as an individual Invenio v3.0 module.

Training value : Web User Interface, D3.js, Python, PostgreSQL, large open-source software development

The duration of this project was 9 weeks, starting *26 June 2017* and ending *25 August 2017*.

ABSTRACT

The CERN Document Server (CDS) is an open-source platform developed at CERN, that provides an online platform for storing and accessing multimedia content regarding High Energy Physics, such as documents, articles, images, videos and other digital scientific material. It is a thin software layer, built on top of Invenio, a digital library framework that enables the construction and management of large-scale digital repositories. Invenio is a highly modular framework,

that consists of multiple individual modules, each providing well-defined services and functionality to client applications.

As in most state-of-the-art applications hosted on the Web, in order to efficiently manage large-scale collections of digital records and simplify administration tasks, it is essential to periodically collect user-related statistics, extract any meaningful information from complex datasets and demonstrate their overview in a both comprehensive and appealing manner.

In this respect, the main objective of this project is to study techniques for visualizing statistics coming from the CERN Document Server, and more specifically design and implement a flexible Invenio module from scratch, needed for the upcoming version of the CDS. The Invenio-Stats-Js¹ module will undertake the task of building interactive graphs and visualizations of user statistics related to CDS records, providing useful feedback about traffic and popularity. The input data for the Invenio-Stats-Js module is retrieved from an already configured Elasticsearch cluster, currently running in production. The integration of such module into the production system of CDS can significantly boost the productivity of developers and also enhance the QoS offered to end-users.

Most of our work was targeted for the new version of CDS Videos (v3.0), which was a top priority during the migration phase. However, since the functionality provided by the Invenio-Stats-Js module is widely applicable in different software environments, it was decided to package it and release it as an independent module on NPM, to facilitate its public distribution, continuous integration and future maintenance.

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¹ <https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio-search-js>

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1. Introduction

➤ Working with large-scale data

There is no escaping from the fact that, in our days, the production rate of digital data is exponentially growing, posing a data management challenge to the research community, currently in the petabyte scale. Experiments currently conducted at CERN, along with all the scientific activities that accompany them, require massive amounts of storage, as well as specialized software platforms to effectively handle all kinds of related digital material.

What's more, data availability and consistency are no longer the only requirements in modern web applications and IT services. The era of 'Big Data` yields for new management principles as far as large data sets are concerned, involving techniques such as information processing, pattern recognition and predictive modeling. These methods of analysis are already considered indispensable in large-scale production deployments and play a significant role in reducing the complexity in the administration process. However, in most cases, a concise and intuitive abstraction is required, since it is almost impossible to study or digest millions of data rows in a short period of time.

This is the point that data visualization comes in to play: it can be regarded as a schematic representation of a large data volume that is usually encoded into visual objects, by stripping away all the noise and focusing on depicting the essence of a given statistical measurement. In this way, data becomes more usable and accessible. Such approach allows for gaining insight into the dynamics of complex data sets, understanding their inner behavior and, thus, leads to optimized decision making in the long run. Therefore, the right visualizations can captivate human attention, save valuable time in development and reveal suspicious activity or interrelations among performance metrics at a glance. In this respect, data visualization contributes to both data exploration and interpretation over time.

➤ Visualizing for the CDS

As expected, the CERN Document Server[1] has to deal with millions of uploaded records, files and thousands of active registered users that interact with it on a daily basis. Based on 2016 records, the CDS hosts around 900k scientific articles, 15k videos (e.g. talks, presentations) and 150k books/proceedings, ranking in the top 10 worldwide, as far as daily page views are concerned.

Thus, at such large scale, the only viable way of perceiving and distinguishing information about these records is to collect real-time statistics related to them and build corresponding visualizations in the form of rich dashboards, that consist of different types of charts, such as line charts, bar charts, pie charts, country maps etc. On the administration side, rich dashboards and interactive graphs facilitate the management of records and collections, demonstrate an all-inclusive overview of the CDS traffic and lead to the adaptation of the underlying infrastructure to the current needs. On the user side, researchers can watch the trend of their uploads, as well as the impact of the individual files

that are associated with their records. In both cases, visualizing statistics certainly leads to improved orchestration of software, allocation of resources and more efficient management of content.

Developing a module for visualizing statistics intended for the CERN Document Server, required deep understanding of its fundamental design principles and constant interaction with various modern technologies, such as Flask[2], Elasticsearch[3], Webpack[4] and D3.js[5]. Our intention to deliver an Invenio module dedicated to building interactive visualizations of statistics stems from the need to improve the quality of management workflows and enlighten both users and maintainers of the CDS about the trend or the popularity of their digital files, records or collections hosted online. That said, the Invenio-Stats-Js module mainly belongs to the explanatory data visualization category, focusing on conveying meaningful insights originating from JSON-formatted data.

In the rest of the document we adequately present all the steps we followed during the development process of the Invenio-Stats-Js module, including theoretical design, selection of technologies, summarized implementation, as well as integration with the upcoming version of the CERN Document Server.

2. Understanding Invenio v3.0 and CDS

➤ Invenio v3.0

Invenio[6] is an open-source framework that comprises of multiple individual modules that provide functionality to client applications, mainly related to digital library management, such as ingestion, classification, indexing and dissemination of data. Various digital data repositories are powered by Invenio, such as the CERN Document Server, the CERN Open Data Repository, Zenodo Research Data Repository and others. In the time of writing, Invenio v3.0 is under development and close to the first stable release. The majority of the Invenio modules are implemented in Python using the Flask microframework, while others are developed in pure Javascript or AngularJS. Core modules involve base, search, authentication, indexing, accounts and others. Depending on the client application, Invenio v3.0 usually needs to provide compatibility and interact with multiple external platforms and services.

In most deployments, it establishes connection with a PostgreSQL[7] database to perform reads, writes and JSON operations, takes advantage of Redis data structure store as a cache and distributes tasks asynchronously using Celery. The internal communication is based on RabbitMQ that provides the message broker, while real-time searches are performed in a distributed fashion upon an Elasticsearch cluster (fast, horizontal scaling, rich features). An overview of services related to Invenio v3.0 is given in Figure1:

Figure1: Invenio v3.0 services

➤ **CERN Document Server (CDS)**

The CERN Document Server(CDS) is one of the biggest open-source IT projects developed at CERN, that allows users to access a large-scale online repository for storing, sharing and retrieving any kind of digital resource, such as documents, reports, journals, videos, scientific material, images etc., most commonly concerning High Energy Physics.

The CDS platform is capable of reliably hosting digital records in multiple formats, while it supports associating numerous file and versions with individual records (e.g. video quality, thumbnails). It is built on top of Invenio, hence it offers operational services like search, upload/download, navigation, authentication, personalization and others. What's more, its flexible metadata facilitate storage and presentation of entities.

In parallel with Invenio v3.0, a newer version of the CDS is currently under development. Thereafter, the current project is going to be integrated into the upcoming release, and can be regarded as a contribution to the Invenio module collection, extending the functionality of the new CERN Document Server.

Bearing in mind that the development of large-scale web applications responsible for managing millions of records is not a trivial task, it is essential to dive a bit deeper into the concepts and architecture of Invenio and the CDS. Both are designed and developed as minimal applications following the structure and principles suggested by Flask. The main goal is to take advantage of blueprints, a design pattern that encourages the definition and reuse of individual components in multiple parts of application instances, along with the initialization of extensions. Blueprints can

greatly abstract complexity, instantiate objects, provide template filtering and act as registry points for operations. It is quite common that the specification of the URLs in a web application is closely associated with the registration of corresponding blueprints.

➤ [Architecture](#)

In order to adequately present the contribution of the current project to the CDS, we provide the following (simplified) architectural diagram. In the bottom layer lies the Elasticsearch cluster that is currently running in production and is responsible for storing and indexing real-time statistics related to records hosted in the CDS platform. Elasticsearch runs in a distributed fashion and involves multiple nodes. In the middle layer lies Invenio v3.0, along with all its modules, while the upper layer hosts an instance of the CERN Document Server.

Figure 2: System Architecture

Our module is intended to co-operate with other Invenio modules, and specifically Invenio-Stats, a module that is currently under development for v3.0. This module implements the backend API for handling all requests that are intended for the Elasticsearch cluster, aiming at retrieving and formatting real-world statistics.

3. [Design and Technologies](#)

Initially, we had to make some fundamental decisions regarding the development of the Invenio-Stats-Js module, concerning its theoretical background and code structure. At the same time, we had to carefully select suitable modern technologies that would be inline with the design principles we relied on, aiming at delivering a modern visualization library for the Web.

➤ [Graphs as ECMAScript6 Classes](#)

At first, based on the fact that most graphical representations share some common attributes or general functionality, we proceeded with the mechanism of classes, that promotes the concept of inheritance. In this respect, we were able to design some abstract graphical visualization templates with standard characteristics, which could later be

extended by individual graphs that require type-specific features or attributes. The integration of classes into the Invenio-Stats-Js module, greatly facilitates not only the expansion of the supported graphs, but also their future maintenance, due to reusability of code and separation of concerns. Hence, we designed an abstract Graph class that could be extended by LineGraph, BarGraph and GroupedBarGraph subclasses, accordingly. Hence, every graph currently supported in the Invenio-Stats-Js module would be represented as a subclass that inherits all core functionality and attributes from the base class.

Having this principle in mind, we decided to work with EcmaScript6[8], which is considered as the future of Javascript and Web Development in general. The main reason was to develop a both backward-compatible and future-proof module, that could be integrated into multiple environments. Furthermore, by developing Invenio-Stats-Js in pure ES6 we were able to utilize various new core features, such as the Object-Oriented Class API (prototypal inheritance), arrow functions (functional style programming), compatibility with both Yarn and NPM package managers, as well as its built-in module system (imports and exports).

➤ [Custom visualization based on D3.js](#)

Before kick-starting this project, we deliberately considered integrating some already available visualization library into CDS v3.0 (like C3.js, Google Charts, chart.js, amCharts, etc.), instead of building a custom one for Invenio. However, there were various good reasons for sticking to a custom implementation. Most importantly, CDS would remain independent of third party library development, avoid enterprise or commercial licenses and, of course, stay open-source. Furthermore, knowing beforehand the requirements for deploying the new version of the CDS, a custom visualization module would certainly provide additional flexibility to the graphs, tailoring them exactly to our needs. Last but not least, importing a large and over-complicated visualization library with numerous dependencies (e.g. jQuery) into the new CDS implementation would add extra burden and points of failure.

Taking the above into consideration, we settled on building the Invenio-Stats-Js module on top of D3.js, the most famous and popular Javascript library for building Data Driven Documents in modern web applications. In our days, D3.js is the de-facto standard for visualizing data on the Web, using well-known standards like HTML, SVG[9] and the DOM. It supports a powerful API that endorses a functional-style programming to perform operations, allowing for element selection, grouping, filtering, mapping, projection, aggregation and others.

What's more, it ships with multiple capabilities, such as automatic scaling, binding of data and transformations of visual elements. Compared to other component-based libraries, it exposes low-level concepts without any abstraction layer, as well as full control over the rendering of data, making it the ideal candidate for a custom visualization library, as it does not rely on high-level interfaces. D3.js is just enough verbose and expressive, granting developers with great freedom over the final result. Finally, it is an open-source project that is under active development and support.

➤ [Node.js environment with Webpack, Karma & Jasmine](#)

Since the functionality provided by the Invenio-Stats-Js module is quite generic, it soon became evident that it could be used not only in favor of the CDS v3.0, but actually in any client instance that is built on top of Invenio and needs some kind of data visualization. Going even further, we decided to package and release the Invenio-Stats-Js module as a standalone Javascript package in the NPM platform, in order to ensure its public availability and automate its installation process.

As expected, developing an Invenio module aimed for publication on NPM required abiding by all modern Web development standards, mainly following the ones suggested by the Node.js[10] community. Therefore, we performed detailed production testing using Karma [11] and Jasmine[12], to verify that our module provides the expected functionality. In addition, we added extensive documentation and tutorials to facilitate deployment and future reference.

The final issues we had to overcome, concerned the need to merge all individual code components into a single module and determine isolated builds for development and production. In order to perform the aforementioned orchestration and packaging operations, we employed the latest version of Webpack (v3.5), one of the most popular open-source bundlers for modern web applications. Its main operation is to dynamically build a dependency graph by parsing the source files, minify scripts and export bundles in the specified module type (CommonJS, AMD, ES2015). By writing a fully-customized configuration for Webpack, and importing various open-source tools and plugins, we were able to avoid much boilerplate, isolate modules and reach optimized results in a fairly automated manner. The most important external tools we used were Babel[13], a transpiler capable of compiling ES6 to ES5 source code for backward compatibility reasons and ESLint[14], a pluggable linting utility to improve code readability and uniformity.

4. Implementation

➤ Graphs

It is notable that classes in ECMAScript6 are technically different from the well-known classes in languages like Java, C++ or Python. The main reason lies in the fact that the former ones are actually an abstraction layer that implements inheritance on top of prototypal inheritance. In essence, defining a subclass in ECMAScript6 creates a tight coupling between object instances underneath, as objects inherit functionality directly from other objects based on prototype chaining.

In this respect, we decided to enclose all common functionality in the `Graph` class and extend it as needed to create more concrete graphs. This class acts as a prototype for our library. By calling `super()` constructor inside the body of subclasses, we were able to form a single-ancestor parent/child hierarchy :

Figure 3: Invenio Graphs as implemented classes

Our first concern was to define the base class. In the constructor function of the `Graph` class both the configuration parsing and the data binding are performed. Then, an empty SVG element is appended in the DOM, while gradually all core elements are populated. More specifically, this general-purpose SVG element contains a horizontal axis, a vertical axis, corresponding X and Y scales, X and Y labels, X and Y ticks, X and Y gridlines, a title and a legend that explains the type of metric that the graph presents.

In addition, aiming at making the graphs interactive and responsive, we implemented various event handler functions that add some critical functionality. Hence, a mouse event handler(`mouseover()`, `mouseout()`) reveals/hides a

dynamically created tooltip element, a `zoom()/pan()` event handler allows users to easily focus on the domain of interest, while a `window.resize()` event handler is responsible for re-rendering graphs in smaller or larger ratios, preserving all information and making all graphs fully responsive. Every graph that our library currently supports (LineGraph, BarGraph, GroupedBarGraph) inherits its core features by calling the corresponding parent class methods, saving critical time and effort. However, child classes need to act autonomously and manipulate input data in a way that produces a different visual result.

```
// Create an empty SVG element in the DOM

super.initialize();

// Parse the current input data

super.parseData();

// Add the horizontal axis

super.makeAxisX();

// Add the vertical axis

super.makeAxisY();

// If configured, add a title to the graph

if (this.config.title.visible) super.makeTitle();

// If configured, add a legend to the graph

if (this.config.legend.visible) super.makeLegend();

// If configured, add a tooltip to the graph

if (this.config.tooltip.enabled) super.makeTooltip();

// Enable zooming by passing the desired zoom handler function
Code snippet 1: Inherit functionality from the base Graph class
```

➤ [Input & Configuration](#)

After reviewing multiple production-ready visualization libraries for the Web, we concluded that one of the most critical features that our module should provide Invenio developers with, is the option to explicitly configure the supported graphs. To achieve that, we introduced a JSON object with standard structure as the default configuration for each type of graph, which can be, of course, overridden during the initialization phase. We argue in favor of JSON format for the configuration of the graphs provided by the Invenio-Stats-Js module, as JSON objects are natively supported in Javascript, while being both human readable and rather intuitive.

```
graph: {
  type: 'line',
  options: {
    curveType: 'curveLinear',
    fillArea: true,
    circles: {
      visible: true,
      radius: 5
    }
  }
}
```

```
y: {
  mapTo: 'value',
  scale: {
    type: 'scaleLinear', format: ''
  },
  options: {
    label: {
      value: 'LabelY', visible: false
    }
  }
}
```


Code snippet 2: Default JSON configuration object (LineGraphConfig)

As far as the input of the graphs is concerned, we implemented a deterministic function that is responsible for parsing and converting raw JSON responses coming from the Elasticsearch cluster into a uniform, pre-specified format, aligned with the latest D3 specifications. When the transformation is completed, we use the D3 API to bind data into document elements, such as bars, circles, rects and paths.

➤ **Usage**

One of our top priorities while developing Invenio-Stats-Js module, was to make it as flexible and convenient for developers as possible. Thus, instantiating interactive graphs and building customized dashboards is just a matter of installing our module via NPM, importing the corresponding classes and feeding them with data. Of course it is required that data is already fetched from the backend, has the correct format and is available for usage.

Instantiating any graph supported in the Invenio-Stats-Js requires 2 mandatory and 1 optional parameters. The mandatory ones involve the dataset and the the HTML DOM element where the graph will be ultimately rendered. The optional one is the JSON configuration object, which overrides the default one in case it is specified. Some basic examples are provided below in order to showcase the usage of our module:

```
// Import as ES2015 module
import { LineGraph } from 'invenio-stats-js';

// Create a line graph in the DOM
new LineGraph(data, 'pageviews').render();
```


Code Snippet 3: Instantiate a LineGraph with default configuration

Figure 4: Single & Multi Line/Area Graphs

```

// Import as ES2015 module
import { BarGraph } from 'invenio-stats-js';

// Create a line graph in the DOM
new BarGraph(data, 'pageviews').render();
    
```

Code Snippet 4: Instantiate a BarGraph with default configuration

Figure 5: Single & Grouped Bar Graphs

The most common use case of the Invenio-Stats-Js module during the migration phase of the CDS Videos was to keep track and visualize the downloads and pageviews of video entries at a given sampling rate. In the near future, more statistics are going to be visualized, such as downloads per individual file related to a given record and statistics per country.

5. Unit Testing and Packaging

Performing unit testing for a visualization library that directly manipulates SVG and DOM elements is not a trivial task, especially when working with complex sets of data. However, it was essential to verify that all graphs that the Invenio-

Stats-Js module produces are correct in terms of value assignment (e.g. height of bars, positions of lines, axis scales) and behave as expected (zooming, tooltips, creation of DOM nodes).

Thus, we performed a series of unit tests for each graph:

- ✓ Verify the creation of the SVG element itself, along with its expected content
- ✓ Check whether event handlers are functional, by mocking `zoom()`, `mousemove()`, `mouseover()` and `mousedown()` events and registering corresponding Spies on the handlers
- ✓ Make sure that the attributes of created elements (e.g. `rects`, `circles`, `paths`) correspond to the expected ones, given a well-known data set beforehand

```
it('should create points at correct coordinates, () => {
  let xScale = graph.getXScale();
  let yScale = graph.getYScale();
  let parsed = parseData(data);

  expect(getCircles().size()).toEqual(parsed[0].data.length);

  parsed.forEach((d, i) => {
    let circles = d3.select(`.${className}`).select('svg').selectAll(`.igj-dot.dot_${i}`);

    for (let idx = 0 ; idx < d.data.length; idx++) {

      expect(xScale(d.data[idx].key)).toEqual(+circles.nodes()[idx].getAttribute('cx'));

      expect(yScale(d.data[idx].value)).toEqual(+circles.nodes()[idx].getAttribute('cy'));

    }
  })
}
```

Code snippet 5: Example of unit test (line.spec.js)

All tests were described in Jasmine, a behavior-driven framework for testing Javascript code and deployed in Karma, an environment that executes test code against browsers and reports success or failure. Our tests were successfully executed in the headless PhantomJS browser, aiming at moving our testing to a continuous integration system.

Meanwhile, we installed a coverage plugin in Karma, in order to have an overview of the percentage of the source code covered in our tests. On average, we performed 10 tests for each type of graph, checking all their core functionality. We achieved a coverage a satisfying percentage close to 85%, which can be improved even more in the future.

Before releasing our module to NPM, we created a `deploy.sh` script in order to deploy our project into TravisCI[16], a hosted and distributed service for testing and building open-source software projects. Additionally, we were able to include our coverage analyzer and dynamically supervise the status of our repository at any time during its development.

6. Integration with CDS v3.0

As already mentioned, this project took place during the migration phase of CDS v3.0 Videos, making this Invenio application the ideal environment for deploying the Invenio-Stats-Js module and testing its performance with real records.

➤ Configuring the development environment

In order to configure the development environment we proceeded with the following actions:

1. Set up a production instance of CDS v3.0 and install all required dependencies in an isolated virtual environment. Additionally, we had configure external services, such as Elasticsearch, PostgreSQL, Celery and Nginx in the local domain and make sure they are up and running.
2. Install required keys and certificates for authentication with the production ES cluster, used by a reverse proxy to pipe network traffic from/to the CDS application instance.
3. Generate bundles and build assets required by the CDS application.

➤ Back-end operations

Since the Invenio-Stats module is not yet integrated into the CDS v3.0, we had to add a new legacy module (Invenio-Stats) that implements all needed back-end operations, mainly involving the establishment of a communication channel with the Elasticsearch cluster. Thus, we implemented a rather simple REST API to serve requests coming from the application layer. In practice, we registered a new blueprint in the Flask application to extend the /api endpoint:

Endpoint	HTTP Method	Statistic
/api/stats/<record_id>/views	GET	Total views of record
/api/stats/<record_id>/pageviews	GET	Aggregated views with timestamps
/api/stats/<record_id>/downloads	GET	Aggregated downloads with timestamps

More specifically, each call to the endpoints above triggers a method that performs the corresponding requests to the Elasticsearch cluster by building them with the Python Elasticsearch Client. The response coming from the production ES cluster was then digested by a dedicated method we implemented into a format that is compatible with the API suggested by the Invenio-Stats module for automatic integration in the future.

➤ Front-end operations

The next step was to create the page that would host the graphs with the stats of individual records stored in the CDS. Thus, we extended the already present Invenio-Records module by adding an extra UI endpoint:

/record/<record_id>/stats

Accordingly, we associated this endpoint with a freshly created markup template (built in Jinja2 engine) that would render each time a HTTP GET request arrived.

In order to fetch the correct JSON data for each record, we implemented a simple .js script to query /api/stats and retrieve the downloads and pageviews of the given record, by performing AJAX calls. This script, together with the Invenio-Stats-Js module and all NPM dependencies were bundled together in a single .js bundle that was ultimately loaded in the Jinja template.

Since both the converted JSON data coming from the backend and the record object itself are available inside the Jinja template, we passed them to the .js bundle and instantiated two different line graphs, as shown below :

Figure 6: Integration in the CDS v3.0 Videos

7. Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion, the main purpose of this project was fulfilled to great extent, since we successfully delivered a production-ready Invenio module for building interactive visualizations for statistics related to the CERN Document Server. The final results were satisfying enough and met all requirements determined during the specification of the project. The integration of the Invenio-Stats-Js module into the upcoming version of the CDS addresses the issue of dealing with verbose JSON formatted data, while it extends the provided User Interface of the CDS with additional functionality and services.

In practice, in collaboration with the Invenio-Stats module, it accomplishes to extract and display useful statistics about individual records, along with associated files in the form of a rich dashboard. To that end, both users and administrators gain insight into the popularity, traffic or unusual events related to digital records at a glance. In the long run, this module expedites the management and supervision of the new CDS, by providing a means of detecting correlations among statistical metric and understanding the average user behavior. Any instance running on top of

Invenio can utilize the Invenio-Stats-Js module, since both front- and back-end applications can benefit from trend analysis.

➤ Future Extensions

Even though the Invenio-Stats-Js module can be already regarded as a standalone and production-ready part of Invenio, we argue that there is always room for further development and improvement.

- During the time window of this project, we did not focus on validating the format of both input and user-specified configuration, since during the migration/testing phase everything was well-defined beforehand. For this operation we could employ JSON-Schema, a vocabulary that allows for annotating and validating JSON documents through specification of data types, properties and structure.
- For the scope of this project, we settled for 2 basic types of graphs. Of course, in the future it would be useful to extend the available graphs with additional categories (such as Country Map, Scatter Plot, Stacked Bar, Stacked Area), especially if there is need to build an all-around observation dashboard that resembles proprietary ones.
- Since there are constant modifications and updates to the new CDS platform, there is need to dive deeper into the styling of the Invenio-Stats-Js module and maybe support further interaction with end-users.

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